

SOME PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF UPCOMING HISTORY TEACHERS

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The pedagogical science and education system of our country has a strategically important task, which is to create all the conditions for education to help improve the health of schoolchildren and students. In this case, the social and pedagogical significance of the formation of a culture of health, which prepares students for the realization of their dreams in life is greatly increased.

When we say about "health culture", we mean a part of the general culture of a person, which includes methods of diagnosing a person's own health, mental and physical condition, a system of knowledge about the concepts that make up a healthy lifestyle; understand that the importance of health and healthy lifestyle values are factors in their personal development; the ability to develop ways to maintain and improve health [2].

Health culture provides a methodological basis for the development of sciences that aim to build human health in a primary way.

ABSTRACT

In this article analyzed the pedagogical, psychological problems of attitudes to health as a value in young people, the formation of health culture and components of a healthy lifestyle, modern trends in health pedagogy.

The contradiction between the culture of health and the denial of an unhealthy lifestyle in the dialectic of an unhealthy lifestyle has led to an increase in human life expectancy, living in his worthwhile living conditions leads him to dedicate his life to good deeds, to the celebration of a healthy lifestyle.

Prolonging human life due to the formation of a culture of health delays death, while living an unhealthy lifestyle shortens human life and accelerates death. At the same time, on the basis of the idea of a perfect man, which embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection of humanity, which has both national and universal significance, it is necessary to carry out the formation of nobility, which always encourages him to goodness. This idea has led all nations to great progress, inspired them to unparalleled achievements in the field of spirituality and enlightenment. There is no future for a people and a nation that does not care about raising a harmoniously developed generation that does not dream of

perfection. The idea of a perfect man has always been a noble dream of our people. Therefore, in our renewed society, the education of a healthy generation, the formation of a free civic spirit, the upbringing of harmoniously developed people by raising spiritual and enlightenment work to a higher level is itself the basis for the formation of a culture of health.

An important factor in shaping a culture of health in the younger generation is to ensure consistency in education, in other words, succession. According to the results of today's research, during the transition from secondary school to vocational education, there will be a negative change in the lifestyle of young people[4].

In many cases, the gradual rise of the education system is accompanied by a sharp change in the lifestyle of young people. There are several reasons for this:

- changes in the social conditions of life, the violation of the rules of work, rest and eating of schoolchildren, there is a mental and emotional stress, adaptation to new conditions is not smooth for everyone;
- training load increases;
- there will be favorable conditions for health problems (the number of smokers, smokers and even alcoholics will increase by 2-2.5 times);
- Combining learning with work (most students start working in stages 1 and 2);
- inactivity, ie a decrease in the level of youth physical activity (80% of students and young people are inactive, which is mainly due to harmful habits of the monitor).

According to the study, the majority of students do not have the basics of health culture: they understand the need for a healthy lifestyle but have not mastered the

skills of maintaining and developing health, there are those who are addicted to harmful habits, and only 30-35% are positive about organized physical activity, physical education and sports. We understand inheritance as the gradual, gradual change of the content, form and methods, technology of teaching and upbringing from one level of education to another in a consistent manner[1].

Inheritance implies that for all levels of education, its main idea, content, methods and organizational forms of teaching and education, methods of determining effectiveness are common.

Inheritance education content planning; rational choice and purposeful combination of methods, forms and means of teaching; adherence to the unity of pedagogical tools and requirements; due to the creation of the necessary conditions for the continuous application and development of mastered learning activities.

Defects in the health of the younger generation The main goal of the state is to be educated, highly qualified, socially oriented, can thwart all efforts to create a quality education system that consists of training a healthy professional.

The set of organizational and pedagogical conditions that ensure consistency in the formation of a culture of health of high school students and students, in our opinion, should be as follows:

1. Creating a health-friendly environment in the educational institution. The implementation of this condition implies the use of means to optimize the workload, the organization of physical activity of students during the school day, the creation of a favorable mental climate, the

introduction of health technologies in the educational process.

2. Sportization physical education of students. Based on the work of a number of researchers, elements of sports are creatively introduced into the field of physical education [3].

3. Assessment of students' physical condition. Regularly monitor the changes in the body of young people engaged in sports, assessment is necessary to optimize the physical loads placed on them.

4. Improving the professional competence of teachers in the formation of a culture of personal health.

5. Develop specific ways to maintain and improve student health. It is based on the results of physical examination of students and the experience of teachers.

According to the above conditions, ensuring consistency in the formation of a culture of health of students can be effectively achieved through the development of cooperation between educational institutions of different levels, combining their efforts towards a common goal.

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